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IN-VITRO DISSOLUTION AND SOME PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF TWO GENERICS OF LEVAMISOLE BOLUS FORMULATIONS FOR LARGE ANIMALS

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ABSTRACT

Physical and dissolution properties of solid oral dosage formulations significantly affect therapeutic outcomes following their use in veterinary medicine. Therapeutic failure of most levamisole boluses for the prevention and treatment of helminth infections have been a recurrent complaint from animal health workers and veterinarians in Nigeria. However, there is dearth of information on the quality of oral bolus formulations of levamisole for veterinary use in Nigeria. Consequently, the purpose of this study was to evaluate physical and dissolution properties of two generic products of levamisole boluses commonly used in large animal practice in Nigeria. Two frequently used generics of levamisole oral boluses for large animal practice (A & B) were evaluated for bolus weight uniformity, hardness, friability, disintegration and dissolution as specified in the United States Pharmacopoeia. The results demonstrated that generic B failed weight uniformity and friability tests, whereas generic A failed friability and disintegration tests. All the products passed dissolution profile test as specified. Consequently, the two products can be used interchangeably, however, generic B is recommended for treating acute enteric helminthiasis because of its fast disintegration and dissolution rates as compared to generic A.

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INTRODUCTION

Infestation with parasitic helminths is one of the most common causes of ill health in domestic animals in the tropics, including Nigeria [1]. In the animal body, gastrointestinal tract is the abode of majority of the helminths, however, some live in tissues. There is array of anthelmintics available in the Nigerian market for prevention and treatment of helminthosis, including Levamisole. Levamisole is an imidazothiazole with a broad spectrum of activity commonly used in ruminants, poultry and pigs [2]. The main objective of an oral tablet is to deliver the drug to the body at a certain rate and defined amount through the gastrointestinal system so that it can produce a pharmacological effect [3]. However, in many situations, solid dosage forms do not give the same desired therapeutic effects. This has been attributed to poor quality parameters such as weight variation, hardness, friability, disintegration time and insufficient dissolution as well as poor absorption of the drug from the gastrointestinal tract [4].

Therapeutic failures following use of most levamisole boluses for prevention and treatment of helminth infestations have been well reported by animal health workers and veterinarians in Nigeria. There is dearth of information on the quality of oral bolus formulations of drugs, including oral levamisole boluses for veterinary use in Nigeria. Consequently, the purpose of this study was to evaluate physical and dissolution properties of two generic products of Levamisole boluses commonly used in large animal practice in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection:

Commonly used boluses of levamisole labeled to contain 600 mg levamisole per bolus were purchased from veterinary drug stores in Kaduna and Ibadan, Nigeria. The labeled shelf-life for the two samples was two years and they were evaluated before their expiry dates. The two samples were identified as A and B.

Physical properties

Twenty boluses from each generic were individually weighed (kg) with an analytical weighing balance (Mettler Toledo, ML303, Switzerland) and the mean weight of boluses for each generic sample calculated. Thereafter, the percentage variations (%SD) from the mean weight were obtained to determine the weight uniformity of boluses for each generic sample. The crushing strength (N) of each bolus was evaluated employing a hardness tester (Copley Mecmesin, UK). Thereafter, five boluses from each generic were dusted, weighed (W_0 kg) and subjected to friability test using a friabilator machine (Copley Scientific, FRV1000, UK) at 60 RPM for 5 minutes. The boluses were subsequently re-dusted, re-weighed (W_1 kg) and the percentage friability (%) calculated as follows:

$$F(\%) = \frac{W_0 - W_1}{W_0} \times 100.$$

Bolus disintegration test was conducted by filling a 900 mL beaker with distilled water at $38 \pm 2^\circ$ C. Five boluses from each of the generics were placed into the basket-rack assembly and connected to a Copley Disintegration Tester (DTG1000, UK). The disintegration time was read when no residue was left in the basket. Thereafter, *in vitro* dissolution testing of the levamisole boluses was determined using a dissolution machine (Copley Dissolution Apparatus, DIS6000, UK) in 5 replicates for each generic. Dissolution medium constituted of USP buffer solutions at pH 6.8 (phosphate buffer solution) and 0.5 % Sodium Lauryl sulphate solution maintained at $38 \pm 0.5^\circ$ C. A 5 mL of dissolution sample was withdrawn at 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 80, 100 and 120 minutes. Concurrently, equal volume (5 mL) of the buffer was replaced to maintain sink condition. Samples were filtered with a $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ nylon filter and assayed by UV spectroscopic method at analytical wavelength of 215 nm as described by Misquith and Dias [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical properties and dissolution characteristics of boluses depend on their packing fraction, including mechanical strength, disintegration and dissolution time which are lowest at the lowest packing fraction and vice versa [6]. An adequate release evaluation of generic drugs promotes interchangeability of these products, to ensure the same pharmacological effect, with the benefit of a lower cost to the patient [7].

Table 1 contains results of the physical properties of two commonly used generics of levamisole boluses in large animal practice in Nigeria. This shows that sample B failed the weight uniformity since the acceptable limit for the weight deviation of 5 % for tablets [8] is exceeded (28 %). The variation of the weight of individual solid formulation indicates corresponding variation in the content of the active pharmaceutical ingredient [9]. Consequently, a bolus from this product will contain 28 % of levamisole in excess of the manufacturer stated content. This increases the chance of drug overdose and toxicity. All the tested generics passed hardness test since their respective crushing strengths were within the acceptable value of >40 N [10]. This shows that these formulations will be able to adequately withstand mechanical shocks during handling in manufacturing, packaging and transportation as reported by Banker and Anderson [11].

The percentage (%) friability test result demonstrates that all the generics failed friability test since the values were above the considerable range of weight loss of <0.5 - 1.0 % for conventional compressed solid dosage formulations [11]. This demonstrates the inability of these formulations to withstand abrasion during packing, handling and transportation. Disintegration is the break down process of tablet into smaller particles and is the first step towards dissolution [12]. Results show that formulation A failed the test since the time for disintegration is 60 minutes which is above the specified 35 minutes [11]. This corroborates with the higher amount of energy needed to crush formulation A (181.27 N) when compared with B (151.83 N)

Table 1: Physical properties of Levamisole hydrochloride boluses for large animals.

Physical property (unit)	Levamisole generic	
	A	B
Weight uniformity (g)	5.49±0.04 (4 %)	5.93±0.28 (28 %)*
Hardness (N)	181.27±29.10	151.83±54.55
Friability (%)	2.5*	2.8*
Disintegration (minutes)	>60*	3.2

*Failed the test.

Figure 1 demonstrates % of levamisole released from the bolus during dissolution profile test. This shows that at 5 minutes, 75 % of levamisole in formulation B was released from the bolus where as it took 30 minutes for the same amount to be released from formulation A. This again corroborates with the shorter disintegration time observed in formulation B (3.2 minutes) as compared to A (>60 minutes) since drug dissolution is facilitated by quick disintegration [13]. Generally, dissolution test is carried out to determine drug release pattern during a specific period of time [14]. This parameter directly relates to the *in vitro* absorption and bioavailability of drug [15]. Even though the two formulations are chemically equivalent, their dissolution characteristics differ. The implication is that the anthelmintic effect of formulation B will be faster than A both locally and systemically. In addition, this result shows that the enteral anthelmintic activity of these products of levamisole cannot be prolonged because of the high rate of dissolution observed.

This study therefore demonstrates that there is a significant variation in the amount of levamisole in the boluses of generic product B. All the test products failed the friability test as specified. However, the two products are used interchangeably for treating helminthosis in large animals where the condition is often not considered as emergency. There is need to routinely conduct post market quality control tests on the available oral boluses for large animal use in Nigeria

Figure 1: Dissolution profile of two generics of levamisole boluses from different sources.

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